

First Stage: Task Assessment

SE1: I will briefly describe my experience with AI systems and models. As a software engineer, I am interested, for example, in how I will store the model. Planning model storage is a task in which software engineers should participate. The model can have multiple artifacts, some of which may be enormous, so they must be stored accordingly. Evaluating and selecting data is not much the software engineer's job, it is much more the data scientist's job. We start to participate more when storing the model and making it available. At least, that was my experience. In some of the activities, we can help the data scientist. For example, I imagine we could provide a spreadsheet with the data. So we are not necessarily working on the system, we are simply helping the data scientists organize themselves. Sometimes we end up helping them because we are friends.

DS1: I think that data access definition should involve the software engineers. Software engineers usually have a greater knowledge of the company's APIs for capturing data, so they should be able to help the data scientists navigate the available infrastructure better. However, this also depends on the role of the data scientist. For example, there are teams where the data scientist is almost a database administrator as well. In this case, a software engineer may not be needed.

DS2: Considering that data may not be in the hands of the data scientist, a software engineer can help understand the best way to access it, when to access it, etc.

DS1: When it comes to ML model evaluation, the data scientists know what metrics are relevant. They will know, for example, if the model is overfitted. If you ask software engineers to deploy an overfitted model, they will probably do it, but only a data scientist will realize that the model has a problem and is not ready for production. Hence, I do not know how a software engineer could help in this process.

SE1: I agree. In my previous work experiences, the data scientists were responsible for evaluating the model and selecting data. In my current project, I have no idea how our ML model was evaluated or how data was selected. In fact, I was never even curious to know. Still, since we have a good relationship with the data scientists, we are always willing to help them if they need it.

DS2: I noticed software engineers are usually not very interested in the research process of a data science application. I have made presentations showcasing the algorithms examined to build a model, or the metrics used for its evaluation, and their attention goes away very quickly. This may be because they do not know how to collaborate much at this stage of research.

DS1: For infrastructure-related tasks, the data scientist will probably not know how to deploy the model, but the software engineer will. The actors in charge of CI/CD operations are usually software engineers. However, this does not mean they know how to execute the model. For this reason, it is vital that a data scientist gets together with them to explain the

model and how to run it. Regarding deployment, I believe both actors need to be in sync to avoid any problems.

DS2: The same goes for MIL model integration tasks. These tasks will define the ML model's output for other system components. This should be discussed between the software engineers and the data scientists, who must evaluate this according to the system's goals.

Second Stage: Recommendation Assessment

1-) Involve data scientists and business owners when eliciting and analyzing requirements

SE1: The business owner knows the data very well. A business owner usually knows how to access the data, whether it is from other systems or from a spreadsheet. I think this interaction is important, especially when defining how data will be acquired and selected. I think the business owner has a lot of knowledge. Sometimes they will know who possesses that hidden spreadsheet that you will need.

DS1: Business owners understand a lot about the data and can help with model evaluation. For instance, sometimes you may think the model has to avoid false positives, but they might say, 'No, my problem is with false negatives,' so then you will have to choose another metric.

DS2: Involving the business owners can help the actors understand what the data represents. Sometimes, you know the name of a given variable and whether it is numeric or categorical, but you may not understand what it represents. For example, I have worked on projects where the data came from another company. In these cases, the business owners had to explain what each data field represented, and this improved the interaction between us and the software engineers.

DS1: Having the business owners close to the software engineers and data scientists during requirements analysis can help enhance their collaboration. For instance, imagine a scenario where the business owner asks for a given accuracy and latency. The data scientist knows how to achieve that accuracy, but may not know if that latency is possible given the available machines. This is something a software engineer can help with.

2-) Provide ML literacy for all project stakeholders

DS1: During data access definition, I do not think knowing the difference between classification and regression would be helpful for acquiring the data.

SE1: This is what I thought. I have been working in an academic environment for a long time. Even though I am not in the AI field, I constantly see lectures and learn about this topic, so I did not require this literacy. Having said that, I do not think this theoretical knowledge is important for data access definition. I think practical instructions, such as how to access a spreadsheet or another system, are more efficient.

DS1: I thought about disagreeing with the following task as well. However, if software engineers happen to know a bit more about data science, they may be able to help with data selection. For example, they may discover noise in the data capable of hindering model training, or notice that a data column has many null values. Nevertheless, I disagree with the statement for defining data access or evaluating the model. These tasks should not induce collaboration. Moreover, I think this recommendation could be interesting for model storage. Comprehending how the models are generated allows you to think about how to persist them more intelligently. For example, suppose there is a high chance of data drifts in the project you are working on. In that case, the software engineer helping with ML artifact storage would know that the model needs to be trained and updated often. This would determine the development of an effective versioning system.

DS2: Yes, depending on the model's characteristics, a software engineer's knowledge could be interesting. Especially when updating the model, I think it would help.

DS1: I feel the same way for the subsequent tasks. ML literacy for software engineers greatly helps in these tasks. They will know, for example, what type of approach to adopt when deploying the model. Depending on the type of model the data scientist has created, the software engineer will have an idea of the computational power required to run it.

SE1: When I voted, I thought this could be the data scientist's responsibility. For example, the data scientist would come and say what the infrastructure requirements are. Then, the software engineer would not need to know anything about AI.

DS1: That is true, their interaction is also important. However, with ML literacy, the software engineer will be able to notice this even if the data scientist forgets to warn the team. This avoids problems in the future, such as having a deployed model with very high latency.

DS2: ML literacy can help with the definition of the model's output and how it will be consumed. It makes communication between the actors easier when specifying the best way to interact with the model.

3-) Develop documentation for product requirements, system architecture, and APIs at collaboration points

SE1: I think documentation always helps, especially for ML model availability. When it comes to data selection, I almost completely disagreed, but I think a requirements documentation may be helpful. However, I have the vision of a software engineer, not a data scientist.

DS2: This recommendation is very relevant for ML model integration and deployment. It is also very useful when defining the model's API.

DS1: I agreed with the statement for most of the tasks. Well-defined product requirements documentation can greatly help with model availability and integration. It can even help with model storage.

SE1: The system architecture documentation mentioned in the recommendation is essential for these tasks. Having that there influenced my votes.

DS1: Yes, exactly. Having well-produced documentation greatly impacts development. For example, if I have a requirement for extremely low latency, it may affect how the model will be developed and made available. The fact that this is documented explicitly assists in the collaboration between the software engineer and the data scientist. For instance, if the data scientist comes up with an extremely slow approach, it will be clear to everyone that the model is not ready for production.

4-) Define clear responsibilities and internal processes with clear boundaries for data scientists and software engineers

SE1: I partially disagreed with the statement for ML model evaluation because it is very clear to me that this is a data scientist's responsibility.

DS1: I agreed because, in my opinion, this recommendation facilitates task division. The data scientist's role can often get confused with other roles. As I mentioned before, they are sometimes also considered database administrators. In addition, they may be confused with software engineers and expected to handle model deployment solely. When you clearly define each role's responsibility, communication becomes easier. This is why I agreed with the statement for all tasks.

DS2: Even if a data scientist will need to perform tasks usually carried out by a software engineer, this needs to be clear for everyone. Clarifying boundaries helps a lot in communication, especially when evaluating the work we need to do. From the point of view of system architecture, these definitions help us visualize who will be responsible for each system component.

SE1: I understand. Still, I maintain my opinion regarding model evaluation. In the teams I have worked in, explicitly defining responsibilities and boundaries was never necessary during this task. Both data scientists and software engineers already knew what was expected from them without the need for a formal explanation. I believe this task should be mostly carried out by data scientists, as there is no need for software engineers to be involved. This may be because I have worked majorly in academic environments.

Moderator: What are the differences related to working in an academic environment?

DS1: In a research environment, roles can be mixed up. For example, I might be in a team where I am the data scientist, and there is someone else who is the software engineer. Because we are in a research environment, the software engineer may also be conducting data science research. This allows them to contribute to the work that I am doing as a data scientist. This is uncommon in industry teams, where roles are more strictly defined. In a research environment, there is a greater knowledge exchange.

5-) Support interdisciplinarity between data scientists and software engineers

SE1: Having another person beside you while working is always useful, especially for catching something you missed. For instance, during data selection, the software engineer might look at the data selected by the data scientist and notice a field that could be included.

DS1: For data access definition, data selection, model evaluation, and model deployment, I think interdisciplinarity is interesting but not vital. I believe a lack of knowledge exchange between the actors during these tasks would not threaten the project. On the other hand, I consider this recommendation important for the other tasks. For artifact storage, for example, both actors need to know how the model was developed and what should be versioned. The same goes for model availability and integration: how to consume the model and its inputs and outputs must be clear to everyone.

DS2: Data scientists are usually more interested in research and generating insights through data analysis, so they may not know how a solution can actually be operationalized and sustained over time. Before deploying to production, it is important to understand what infrastructure is available, how the model will be updated, and how data will be continuously obtained. I think this kind of knowledge is more related to software engineering. As data scientists become familiarized with these concepts, their communication with software engineers will improve.

SE1: I agree. If the data scientists know how model deployment works, they can design the ML model with this process in mind. This would make the deployment task less arduous, especially if the project is still in its initial phase.

DS2: After the system is deployed and operational, the actor responsible for maintaining it is usually a software engineer, not a data scientist. This recommendation motivates the software engineer to know more about model characteristics, such as if it is a separate service or how it is consumed. This knowledge would be very helpful, for example, if the software engineer notices an opportunity to implement incremental learning.

6-) Organize regular meetings for showcasing team activities

SE1: When defining data access and selecting data, I think the meetings would help. For the other tasks, I consider regular meetings useful, but not critical. After the team has agreed on all definitions, an occasional conversation between members should be enough. Even if they are not that frequent, they would be enough to ask questions and answer doubts.

DS1: I love daily meetings because they bring team members from different areas together to witness the whole project's evolution. For tasks that require a greater synergy between software engineers and data scientists, I agree that there should be regular meetings to keep everyone up to date. However, for tasks where I do not see such a strong synergy, I believe these meetings are nice to have so that everyone knows what is happening, but they are not crucial. In the case of data selection, for example, having a meeting to discuss this task would be good for the software engineers to be more informed about what is happening, but it is not essential for their work. The same is true for data access definition: showcasing how data is obtained might be interesting for data scientists, but they do not have to know where the data comes from as long as they have access to it. In these scenarios, I feel the team's progress would not be compromised if these meetings did not happen.

DS2: I agreed with the statement because of the team alignment generated by this recommendation. The team must know what is being done and how this impacts the tasks.